

Quantified Democratic System

A combination of technology, mathematics, and politics in this new digital era

Abstract

Internet and social networks are enabling an electronic democratic system where people openly express their political opinions on an unprecedented scale as never seen before. These digital opinions or electronic votes make it possible for people and the government to become closer, more connected, and more transparent.

Body

Quantified Democratic System is a theoretical political system where all citizens are allowed to vote but these votes are not equal but quantified.

This theoretical approach in politics is somewhat occurring nowadays, even though it's not entirely precise as the above definition explains. People, especially on social media, express their opinions about various issues that concern them. So in a sort of way they "vote" using their opinions but what they don't realize is that these opinions don't have the same impact compared with other opinions. This impact can be somewhat quantified.

Example

To give an illustration: we have two different persons on a social network (Bob and Sally) who express two different opinions about a specific issue. Bob is in favor of that issue and has an audience of 22k members on his profile (his followers) while Sally is against that issue but has an audience of only 1.7k members (her friends and followers) on her social media account. So basically we have a virtual vote about that issue that both concerns them but their impact is different since they influence different audiences (Bob influences about 22k persons while Sally only 1.7k). So their "vote" is quantified differently.

Conclusion

This approach creates an electronic/virtual system where people express their opinions (votes) but these aren't equal but quantified; users with bigger audiences influence more than people with lower audiences. In simple words, the "voting" process is unequal but differentiated.

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